

BEHAVIOUR OF BRICK MASONRY COLUMNS CONFINED WITH FERROCEMENT JACKETING UNDER AXIAL COMPRESSION

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Abstract:

Masonry is an essential construction component, serving as either load-bearing or infill material in reinforced concrete or steel-framed buildings. Usually brick masonry columns are capable of withstanding axial loads but they are weak in carrying lateral loads. Due to the increase in population density in rural areas, vertical extension of existing buildings featuring load-bearing masonry columns are essential. As a result, the capacity of these masonry columns needs to be increased. The confinement technique has been effectively used to enhance the strength and ductility of structural elements. Since masonry possesses relatively limited ductility and tensile strength, the confinement has been shown to improve the performance of masonry elements, particularly the columns. Although the techniques have shown to provide confinement and improve the performance of masonry columns, each has its own advantages and disadvantages in terms of applicability, compatibility, strength enhancement, ductility gain and reversibility. Therefore in this paper, an attempt has been made to critically review the performance of masonry columns plastered with biosilica and polypropylene fibre and confined with ferrocement jacketing to appraise their performances in relation to various parameters. ANSYS 20.2 has been used to develop the confined compressive strength and axial stress strain behaviour of the masonry columns. Subsequently the predictabilities of the analytical models were verified by comparing against with the experimental database. ANSYS results revealed that the analytical models perfectly replicate the confined strength of masonry columns. Therefore, it can be recommended to use deliberately across different confinement techniques investigated.

Keywords: ANSYS, Brick, Masonry, Confinement, Ferrocement Jacketing, Strength Enhancement

1.INTRODUCTION

Masonry structures have been considered ideal in the construction owing to their strength, appealing look, and cost effectiveness. Brick masonry has been widely used as load-bearing elements in low rise buildings. However there have a number of causes those leads to make structures weaker such as inferior construction, settlement of foundation, deterioration of strength of the construction material due to aging, etc. With the increase in the population and urbanization accelerating, the demand for vertical expansion is being increased. In those cases, there are two ways to get rid of this kind of situation, one is dismantling of the existing structure and then make a new one for the desired population. The other and viable option is to strengthen the old structure and make things easy for accommodating the desired population. Traditional methods such as RC jacketing, grouting cracks and voids, stitching with metallic or brick elements, post-tensioning with steel ties, shotcrete jacketing, ferrocement, and center core retrofitting are available for retrofitting existing masonry structures(1-25).Among these techniques, ferrocement jacketing has emerged as a promising method due to its less cost, effectiveness and utility. Unreinforced brick masonry columns experience transverse expansion when subjected to compressive loads. Due to the varying stiffness of the two materials and the strong bonding behaviour between them, the lateral deformation of the mortar is often greater than that of the brick units. This leads to axial compression and bilateral stress on the brick units, resulting in the rapid development and propagation of vertical cracks. Several reinforcing techniques have been used on masonry columns to limit the transverse expansion of the material and enhance its strength and deformability.

Garg carried out a study which shows that ferrocement is highly effective in restoring strength of damaged brick masonry columns and damaged structures can be repaired using ferrocement as long as it has not collapsed. According to observations, there is very little time between the first visible crack and the eventual failure of a plain brick wall, but in the case of a ferrocement encasing, the failure happens much later than the first visible crack. This suggests that the ferrocement jacketing bears the initial axial compressive load, and its failure is seen before the core fails. There is also a lot of variety in the brick masonry's elastic modulus value. In this work, S.V. Venkatesh attempted to ascertain whether encasing damaged brick masonry walls with ferrocement would boost their load carrying capacity. Tests on brick masonry walls with various shapes, bonding, and ferrocement mesh anchoring techniques are the focus of the inquiry. The crack's width, pattern, initial crack, and final load were recorded. According to research done by Nandakumar, Revathi, and Revathi, the addition of ferrocement casing to a

structure adds strength because bricks cannot support significant lateral loads. Tests on a mesh-free column with ferrocement casings that were 1 mm, 0.707 mm, and 0.354 mm thick revealed that the compressive strengths that were 1.05, 1.04, and 1.42 times greater than those of the mesh-free column. The investigation came to the conclusion that ferrocement jacketing increases the compressive strength of brick masonry columns because the encased specimen consistently displayed higher compressive strength.

Naaman (2000) described the distinctive physical and mechanical properties of ferrocement. Ferrocement has high tensile strength and stiffness due to the confinement with two-dimensional reinforcement of the mesh system and undergo large deformations before cracking or high deflections before collapse. Khan and Monem (2007) studied the composite behaviour of brick masonry column encased with ferrocement having one, two and three layers of wire mesh with some bonding agent on the surface. Results indicated a significant strength enhancement of those columns. An increase of 19% and 21% reported for the first crack load and ultimate load respectively compared to the control specimen (Shah, 2011). Henceforth in this current paper, the authors present the usage of ferrocement jacketing as an effective method to enhance the axial capacity and deformation ability of unreinforced brick masonry columns.

2. RESEARCH GAP IDENTIFICATION AND OBJECTIVES

Although an extensive research has been carried out in understanding the masonry columns under axial compression, very limited studies are focussing on incorporating mortar and confinement effects in strengthening columns. Previous studies, offer valuable insights but are constrained by practical limitations and material variability. This study aims to bridge this gap by conducting a controlled and comprehensive investigation using finite element analysis. By directly comparing experimental data with FEM results, the study will validate numerical models and enhance understanding of masonry column behaviour. This integrated approach will improve the accuracy of finite element models, optimize design and construction practices, and ultimately contribute to safer and more efficient masonry structures.

3. MATERIAL PROPERTIES

The experimental program included 8 Non modular brick masonry columns that were evaluated under an axial compression load. Materials for the study included Ordinary Portland Cement (OPC 53 grade) with a specific gravity of 3.15 and surface area of 290 m²/kg, conforming to IS 12269:1987 , for control mortar; manufactured sand (fine aggregate) meeting IS 383:2016 standards with a specific gravity of 2.80, water absorption of 0.42%. Non-modular clay bricks,

conforming to IS 1077:1992 , with a density of 15.69 kN/m³,water absorption of 16.12%, and average compressive strength of 5.31 N/mm², were used for masonry columns. Machine-welded wire mesh (20x20mm, 0.75mm thickness) conforming to ASTM A185 served as confinement and the stress-strain curve is illustrated in the Figure 1. Mortar cubes were tested for compressive strength as per IS 4031 (Part 6) – 1988 [30], with control mortar achieving 14.93 N/mm².

(a) Ferrocement Jacket

(b) Polypropylene Fibres

(c) Biosilica

(d) Non modular bricks

(e) Ordinary Portland cement

Fig.1. Materials involved in the present study

4. TEST SETUP

Specimen Preparation and Test Setup

A total of 8 masonry columns were fabricated, encompassing 4 distinct combinations with two replicates for each. These columns had a uniform length of 1200 mm but varied in cross-sectional dimensions as outlined in Table 2. Selected columns were furnished with surface coatings [NBC-Brick column plastered with conventional mortar; NBC-1-Brick column plastered with Biosilica and Polypropylene fibre wrapped with a single layer of welded wire mesh; NBC-2-Brick column plastered with Biosilica and Polypropylene fibre wrapped with double layer of welded wire mesh] for confinement. Figure 2 illustrates the preparation of specimen and Table 2 depicts the important properties of the materials involved in the present study before casing the columns. Fig.3 represents the stress strain characteristic of the welded wire mesh. Post-curing, all specimens were primed, marked, and transported to the testing facility for axial compression trials.

Table 2 Details of Specimens

S.No	Designation of columns	Cross section	No.of layers	Description of Columns
1	UBC	230 x 230 mm	-----	Unconfined Brick masonry column
2	NBC	230 x 230 mm	-----	Brick masonry column with Conventional Plastering
3	NBC-I	280 x 280 mm	1	Brick masonry column plastered with Biosilica and Polypropylene fibre confined by a single wire mesh
4	NBC-II	280 x 280 mm	2	Brick masonry column plastered with Biosilica and Polypropylene fibre confined by double wire mesh

Fig. 2. Preparation of column specimens

Table 3 Properties of Materials involved in the present study

S.No	Properties	Results	Limits	IS standards
	Cement			
1	Fineness(m ² /kg)	290	>225	(IS 269:2015)
2	Specific Gravity	3.10	3.15	IS 4031 (Part II) – 1988
3	Standard Consistency	34	33-35	IS:4031-Part4-1988
4	Initial Setting Time(minutes)	30	30	IS:4031-Part4-1988
	Msand			
1	Water absorption %	0.42	0.3% to 2.5%	IS 383 (1970)
2	Specific Gravity	2.80	2.3 -2.9	IS 2386 (Part 3): 1963
3	Fineness modulus	2.90	2.3 to 3.1	IS 383: 2016
	Bricks			
1	Water absorption %	16.12	20	IS 1077 (1992)
	Density (kN/mm ²)	15.69	25	IS 2180:1988
	Compressive strength (N/mm ²)	5.31	>3.5	IS 1077:1992
	Biosilica			
	Specific Gravity	2.3	2.2-2.3	No Specific code
	Polypropylene fibre			
1	Specific Gravity	0.9		IS 10951:2020
2	Length of fibre	6 mm		

Fig. 3. Stress strain curve of wire mesh

The experimental setup, illustrated in Figure 4, employed a 500 kN hydraulic press to subject column specimens to axial compression. Steel end caps (20 mm thick) distributed the load evenly across specimen tops. Compression loading was applied incrementally (approximately 2.5 kN increments) until failure. Displacement was monitored using four horizontal and one vertical linear variable differential transformer (LVDT). Specimens were loaded under a monotonically increasing vertical load until failure. During testing the cracking load, failure pattern and axial deformation were observed for each specimen and duly recorded.

5. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Experimental Load versus Displacement

The experimental results reveal distinct differences in load bearing capacities and deformation behaviours among the various masonry column specimens. These differences are primarily due to variations in material properties, confinement effectiveness, and construction quality. Figure 5 presents the tested specimens' axial and lateral load-displacement curves, highlighting the performance variations. The first cracking and ultimate loads of different columns are presented in Table 4 along with displacements in X, Y and Z directions. As anticipated, the average first cracking load was lower for the control brick masonry column. In contrast to the control specimens, the average first cracking loads of the columns showed a significant increase when reinforced with ferrocement jacketing. The enhancement percentage for brick column plastered with conventional mortar is about 106.5% greater than unconfined brick column. Similarly the enhancement percentages for single layered and Double layered ferrocement Jacketed brick column (Plastered with Biosilica ,polypropylene fibre combined with Conventional Mortar) are about 304% and 339% greater than unconfined brick column. The Unconfined Column (UBC) demonstrated a load capacity of 46 kN, with deformations in

X, Y and Z directions are 0.68, 5 and 0.86 mm respectively. These results indicate a lower structural performance, emphasizing the limited load bearing ability and susceptibility to deformation in the absence of confinement. Column NBC demonstrated a higher load capacity of 95 kN, with deformations in X, Y and Z directions 0.84, 5.30 and 0.94 mm respectively by holding bricks together, preventing individual brick movement, resisting shear forces, and improving overall stiffness and stability, which can also delay crack propagation. Column NBC-I demonstrated a load capacity of 186 kN, with deformations in X,Y and Z directions 1.52 ,7.00 and 1.54 mm respectively. It prevents outward expansion and cracking under axial load. The mesh acts as a hoop, restraining the brickwork and forcing it into a state of triaxial compression, which enhances the material's strength and load-bearing capacity. This confinement also improves the column's ductility, resistance to seismic loads, and overall structural performance by delaying crack initiation and propagation. . Column NBC-2 demonstrated a load capacity of 202 kN, with deformations in X,Y and Z directions 1.80 ,7.50 and 1.85 mm respectively .This confinement prevents premature failure by improving the structural integrity and resistance to deformation, leading to a more robust and ductile response to stress. Fig. 5 presents the tested specimens' axial and lateral load-displacement curves.

Table 4. Experimental Observations

S.No	Designation of columns	P_{cr} (kN)	$P_{u,}$ (kN)	Δ_{UY} (mm)	Δ_{UX} (mm)	Δ_{UZ} (mm)
1	UBC	25	46	5.00	0.68	0.86
2	NBC	65	95	5.30	0.84	0.94
3	NBC -I	110	186	7.00	1.52	1.54
4	NBC-II	124	202	7.50	1.80	1.85

(a) UBC

(b)NBC

(c) NBC-I

(d) NBC-II

Fig.5 Failure of Brick Masonry Columns

Fig.6 Load versus Axial deflection of Columns (Exp)

Modes of Failure

Figure 6 presents the failure modes observed in the tested masonry column specimens, revealing how different confinement techniques and materials affect their structural response under axial compression. The failure mechanisms provide valuable insights into the behaviour of the columns, which are crucial for understanding their structural performance and optimizing design strategies. UBC column exhibited brittle failure characterized by vertical cracks running along the column's height. These cracks resulted from the crushing of the masonry material, indicating that the unconfined column could not effectively distribute or absorb the applied loads, leading to a sudden and catastrophic failure. The brittle nature of this failure mode underscores the limitations of unconfined masonry columns in withstanding axial loads. Confined Columns (NBC, NBC1 and NBC2) showed similar brittle vertical cracking as seen in the UBC column, but the presence of conventional masonry provided some degree of confinement, resulting in slightly improved load-bearing capacity. The appearance of corner cracks, or the "knife effect," suggests that stress concentrations at the column's corners led to localized failure and detachment of the surface-coated mortar. These cracks indicate that conventional masonry can enhance load capacity, it may not be sufficient to prevent localized failures under increased loads. NBC-I and NBC-II experience a complex failure mode due to increased levels of confinement. The formation of both vertical and horizontal cracks, along with significant horizontal crack propagation, was observed. However, the horizontal cracks

and mortar detachment in these specimens highlight significant structural distress, demonstrating that even with added confinement, the columns are vulnerable to shear forces under axial compression.

6. FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS (FEA) IMPLEMENTATION

For unplastered columns, the FEA results showed good agreement with the experimental load–displacement graph, showing similar peak load and stiffness. The load–displacement curves can be divided into two stages, i.e. loading up to first-crack and further loading up to failure. Fig.7 presents the modelling of columns and Table 5 presents the data given as input in the analysis. Comparing the first stage, it was observed that the stiffness of the FE model was higher than the experimental work in general for fibrous plaster columns. Minor cracks are normally formed during the setting time of plaster and are known as shrinkage cracks. These little cracks are dispersed and gradually grow into a larger, more noticeable crack as the applied lateral load increases.. However, the FEA model was based on using the smeared crack method, which means that cracks due to shrinkage were not captured. Therefore, the stiffness of the FE models was higher than the experimental tests in the first stage of crack formation for fibrous plaster columns. Comparing the displacement of the experimental results and FE predicted values, it can be seen that the FE models accurately projected the displacement in general for all cases. Post-peak-load behaviour was not compared with FE models as there were not enough data available from the experimental results. The experimental results of failure load F_{EXP} and the FE predicted values F_{ANSYS} for all specimens are presented in Table 9. The FE predicted value is the maximum force which can be calculated as the sum of the reactions at the point of application of loading. The FE prediction values were in good agreement with the experimental results for all cases within 15% difference. The rotating crack model assumes that cracking always occurs within principal planes, and it does not consider internal shear contribution across the crack plane. Therefore, it was expected to obtain a lower value of failure load from FE models than the experimental value. In this section, the results of the comparison between the ANSYS output and the experimental work are presented. The comparative study was undertaken to determine the validity of the finite element models in predicting the nonlinear behaviour of the unplastered, plain-plastered and Plastered with Biosilica and polypropylene fibre with wrapping of ferrocement Jacketing. The results of the comparative study between ANSYS models and experimental works are presented with the help of graphs and displacement profiles (Fig .8, Fig.9 and Fig.10) and Table 6 explains the percentage of accuracy of Experimental values and FEA values.

Table 5 Input Properties of Specimens

Material	Brick	NM	NMBP	Wire mesh
Element Type	Solid 185	Solid 65	Solid 65	Link 180
Compressive strength (N/mm ²)	5.31	14.93	25	
Elastic modulus (N/mm ²)	5000	15000	30000	140
Poisson's ratio (ν)	0.2	0.22	0.21	0.3
Tensile strength (N/mm ²)				450
Yield strength (N/mm ²)				420

Where NM-Normal mortar; NMB-Normal mortar with 10% Biosilica; NMBP-N= Normal mortar with 10% Biosilica and 0.5% Polypropylene fibre

Fig.7 FE Modelling of Brick Masonry Columns

Table 6 Comparison between FEM and Experiment Results

Column Designation	Load (P_{cr})			Load (P_u)			Axial Deformation		
	Exp (a)	FEM (b)	% diff	Exp (a)	FEM (b)	% diff	Exp (a)	FEM (b)	% diff
UBC	25	23	8.00	46	50	8.70	2.40	2.50	4.17
NBC	65	60	7.60	95	100	5.26	4.80	5.00	4.17
NBC-I	170	155	8.80	186	170	8.6	6.00	5.60	6.67
NBC-II	196	170	13.2	202	186	7.9	6.50	6.00	7.69

Fig.8 Load versus Axial deflection of UBC and NBC(FEM and Exp)

Fig.9 Load versus Axial deflection of NBC-I and NBC-II (FEM and Exp)

Fig.10 Displacement of Brick Masonry Columns(FEA)

7.CONCLUSION

Brick columns are inherently limited in ductility because bricks have low tensile and shear strength, making them prone to brittle failure under seismic or lateral loads, especially in tension and torsion. This fundamental weakness, inherent in the masonry material itself, leads to a brittle failure mode characterized by cracking and disintegration rather than gradual deformation. While confinement techniques like jacketing can improve performance and even introduce some ductility, unconfined brick columns are generally brittle and lack the ability to undergo large inelastic deformations before failure. Strengthening using Ferrocement overlay has shown to be a viable and efficient way to reinforce different kinds of brick masonry columns. The investigation showed that the brick masonry columns' performance significantly improved after going through the strengthening process. The first cracking strength of NBC-I averaged a surprising of 138% improvement, than NBC. Further highlighting the efficiency of ferrocement overlay strengthening, the ultimate strength of the strengthened columns showed an average increase of 304% in comparison to the control specimens. Notably, in comparison to the control specimens, the strengthened columns showed an average increase in deformation ability of 150%, clearly demonstrating their improved ductility. These outcomes show that ferrocement overlay is a practical and applicable technique for bolstering and increasing load-bearing capability.

References:

1. Al-Rawe, H. S., Tawfiq, S. A., and Al-Shaikhi, S. (2024). Experimental and analytical investigations on biaxially loaded RC columns retrofitted with ferrocement jacketing. *Journal of University of Babylon for Engineering Sciences*, 32(1), 25–38.
2. Amala, M., Gowri, S., and Kumaravelu, G. (2021). Strengthening of compression member by ferrocement with glass fibres for seismic retrofit. *Structures*, 30, 1396–1407.
3. ASTM International. (2002). *Standard Specification for Steel Welded Wire Reinforcement, Plain, for Concrete*. ASTM A185-02. West Conshohocken, PA: ASTM.
4. Bakhteri, J. (2004). Finite element modelling of structural clay brick masonry subjected to axial compression. *Jurnal Teknologi (Sciences & Engineering)*, 40(1), 1–10.
5. Bureau of Indian Standards. (1987). *Specification for 53 Grade Ordinary Portland Cement*. IS 12269:1987. New Delhi: BIS.
6. Bureau of Indian Standards. (1988). *Methods of Physical Tests for Hydraulic Cement: Part 6 Determination of Compressive Strength*. IS 4031 (Part 6):1988. New Delhi: BIS.
7. Bureau of Indian Standards. (1992). *Specification for Common Burnt Clay Building Bricks*. IS 1077:1992. New Delhi: BIS.
8. Bureau of Indian Standards. (2016). *Specification for Coarse and Fine Aggregate for Concrete*. IS 383:2016. New Delhi: BIS.
9. Garg, Amit. (2009). *Ferrocement applications in repair and retrofitting of brick masonry columns*. Shodh Bhagirathi, Indian Institute of Technology Roorkee [Thesis/dissertation].
10. Kaish, Ahmad B. M., Alam, M. Mahmud, Jamil, Md. T., and Zain, Md. F. M. (2012). Axial capacity and deformation ability of ferrocement-jacketed brick masonry columns. *Construction and Building Materials*, 32, 138–147.
11. Kaish, Ahmad B. M., Alam, M. Mahmud, and Jamil, Md. T. (2018). Ferrocement composites for strengthening of concrete columns: a review. *Construction and Building Materials*, 163, 255–271.
12. Khan, M. Monemul, Monem, M. A., Shah, A. A., Saha, S. K., and Rahman, S. M. (2007). Behavior of ferrocement encased brick masonry columns. *Journal of Structural Engineering*, 133(12), 1767–1775.
13. Kksal, H. O., and Yazgan, U. (2012). Elastoplastic finite-element analysis of FRP-confined masonry columns. *Journal of Composites for Construction*, 16(4), 389–398.
14. Liu, Hongyao, Lei, Min, and Chen, Bowang. (2020). Experimental study on axial compression behavior of masonry columns strengthening with bamboo scrimber bar mesh mortar layer. *Advances in Civil Engineering*, 2020, 3473452.
15. Mansour, W., and El-Sayed, M. (2025). Evaluation of the axial compressive response of reinforced concrete brick columns using finite element analysis. *Journal of Civil Engineering and Architecture*, 12(6), 4230–4256.
16. Naaman, Antoine E. (2000). *Evolution, physical, and mechanical properties of ferrocement and thin cement composites*. Proceedings of the International Ferrocement Society, Ancona, Italy, 1–28.
17. Nandakumar, V., Revathi, K., and Revathi, M. P. (2019). Study of ferrocement in strengthening of brick masonry columns. *International Journal of Engineering Development and Research*, 7(1), 282–286.

18. Saingam, P., and Nanthavubarn, K. (2023). Enhancing the flexural behavior of brick masonry walls with ferrocement jackets. *Structures*, 51, 67–77.
19. Shah, Abid Ali. (2011). Applications of ferrocement in strengthening of unreinforced masonry columns. *International Journal of Geology*, 53, 99–106.
20. Sneed, L. H., Noor-E-Khuda, Negar, Ghiassi, Behzad, and Raza, Sohail. (2019). Compressive behavior of brick masonry columns confined by fiber-reinforced cementitious composites. *Journal of Composites for Construction*, 23(3), 04019015.
21. Syril, R. Jose Antony, and Rajkumar, D. (2024). Experimental investigation of ferrogeopolymer confinement for enhancing brick masonry column resilience under axial compression. *SSRG International Journal of Civil Engineering*, 11(4), 80–91.
22. Venkatesh, S.V. (2010). Strength characteristics of brick masonry wall before and after encasing with ferrocement. *Proceedings of the 8th International Masonry Conference, Dresden, 2010*, pp. 1–8.
23. Yavartanoo, F., and Rafezy, B. (2022). Dry-stack masonry wall modeling using finite-element micromodeling approach. *Journal of Structural Engineering*, 148(8), 04022143.
24. Zhang, Pu, Shaohua, Fan, Ye, Liu, Ahmed, Sheikh Shamim, Junmin, Hu, and Chang, Su. (2024). Axial compressive performance of masonry columns strengthened with ECC jacket and FRP strips. *Engineering Structures*, 301, 115832.
25. Jing, Jiapeng, Hao, Hongwei, Wang, Liming, and Peng, Zhenyu. (2023). Compressive behavior of brick masonry columns confined with high-strength fiber-reinforced concrete. *Structures*, 54, 532–542.